

***What Iranians Want* by Arash Azizi, 2024, Oneworld Publications, 256 pp., £20.00, ISBN: 9780861547111 (hbk)**

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In the months that followed the killing of Jina (Mahsa) Amini at the hands of the Iranian ‘Morality Police’ on September 16, 2022, tens of thousands of protestors gathered from Tehran to Vancouver to protest the Islamic Republic of Iran. Jina’s story sparked widespread outrage not because it was shocking but rather because it was so *ordinary*—in a country where many women have experienced harassment and arrests due to “bad hijab”, their crimes ranging from loose scarves to tight jeans—Jina’s story could have been anyone’s. As more young women gathered to take off their hijabs, cries for Women, Life, Freedom, or Zan, Zendegi, Azadi (itself a translation of the Kurdish Jin, Jiyar, Azadi), spread throughout the streets of Iran.

Arguing that these protests indicate an “irrevocable” change in Iran’s future, Arash Azizi presents a history of Iranian activism and dissent since the 1979 Islamic Revolution. Written in an accessible way, Azizi’s book is appropriate for lay readers without much prior knowledge about Iran’s complex historical, sociopolitical, and cultural context. In addition to focusing on the fight for women’s rights, *What Iranians Want* touches on seven other themes that show the fight against various facets of authoritarian rule, such as the environment, economy, and organized labour. Accordingly, the 2022 uprisings erupted out of growing dissatisfaction with the constant encroachments of the regime and the burning desire for a “normal life” across Iranian society.¹ Azizi claims that “decades of daily resistance” to the Islamic Republic’s hijab laws, among other acts of defiance (e.g., publicly lamenting the government or singing in public parks), finally culminated in a new *women’s* revolution.²

The first two chapters provide a concise overview of the fight against compulsory hijab and women’s rights since the Islamic Republic’s inception. Azizi argues that Khomeini made his hard-line stance on women clear in a 1979 interview, in which he maintained that ‘progressive’ Islam does not consist of “going to the movies and dance clubs.”³ Later that year, Khomeini’s government rolled back the Family Protection Law, which granted women the right to divorce and child custody, and subsequently passed comprehensive hijab laws in 1983. As is characteristic of the book, Azizi spends the remainder of these chapters detailing the stories of different activists (e.g., Narges Mohammadi and Sepideh Qolian),⁴ organized movements (e.g., the One Million Signatures campaign against discriminatory legislation),⁵ and key International Women’s Day celebrations (e.g., at the University of Tehran and in Evin prison).⁶ Azizi also demonstrates the severity of structural impediments to political

¹ Arash Azizi, *What Iranians Want: Women, Life, Freedom* (London: Oneworld, 2024), 33, 206.

² Azizi, 33.

³ Azizi, 12.

⁴ Azizi, 36, 41.

⁵ Azizi, 40, 58.

⁶ Azizi, 19, 36.

progress, exemplified by the Guardian Council's blockage of the international CEDAW⁷ treaty following its ratification by the reformist Khatami government in 2003.⁸ In doing so, Azizi compellingly connects the 2022 uprisings to a tradition of women's protests in Iran while also explaining the break with prior reform-minded movements, which had sought to use government channels to advocate for women's rights. The book's references to specific names, slogans, and conversations further humanize the grievances of Iranian activists over time, grounding them in the activists' first-hand experience of oppression and relatable desire for sociopolitical liberty. As such, Azizi's narrative method of displaying overlapping moments of activism among women from diverse political backgrounds supports his concluding argument that the 2022 uprisings were uniquely non-ideological and instead driven by a desire for a "normal life."

In his chapters on the fight for labour unions, freedom of religion, and refugee rights, Azizi compellingly traces the strength of the uprising to the margins of society. On November 15, 2022, steelworkers in Isfahan walked out of factories in support of the protests, setting off a series of strikes that expanded in the following weeks to oil workers in Mahshahr, aluminium workers in Bandar Abbas, and petrochemical workers in Sanandaj.⁹ Viral videos of shuttered shops and chanting labourers sparked excitement among spectators who were reminded of the successful oil strikes of 1979. Though the Islamic Republic's neoliberal policies have deteriorated unions and outlawed independent labour organizing,¹⁰ thereby lessening the impact of the walk-outs as contract workers were forced to return to work to put food on the table, these strikes nonetheless invigorated the 2022 movement.¹¹ Further, rather than following long-established union leaders, the 2022 strikes saw the rise of local figures, such as Esmayil Bakhshi, a millennial from Dezful who became popular among his fellow workers at the Haft-Tappeh Sugarcane Factory.¹² Highlighting his local accent and down-to-earth personality, Azizi reveals how the 2022 uprisings drew strength from the voices of the marginalized, who could not easily be dismissed as 'outside agitators' by the Islamic Republic's forces, which is a common tactic used to discredit protestors.¹³

The broad reach of the uprisings—which set them apart from the 2009 Green Movement that appealed to the urban middle class or the 2019 Oil Protests that were concentrated in the working-class provinces—also mobilized marginalized ethnic and Sunni communities in Sistan-Baluchestan and Zahedan.¹⁴ Home to Baloch, Kurdish, Lur, and other ethnic groups, these provinces have faced decades of economic and social repression. Efforts undertaken by the state to vilify these groups were under-

⁷ Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women.

⁸ Azizi, *What Iranians Want*, 50.

⁹ Azizi, 63, 67.

¹⁰ Eskandar Sadeghi-Boroujerdi, "Iran's Uprisings for 'Women, Life, Freedom': Over-Determination, Crisis, and the Lineages of Revolt," *Politics* 43, no. 3 (August 2023): 427, <https://doi.org/10.1177/02633957231159351>

¹¹ Azizi, *What Iranians Want*, 69.

¹² Azizi, 83.

¹³ Azizi, 85.

¹⁴ Azizi, 133, 140.

mined by the deaths of innocent protestors like Khodanoor Lojei, a 26-year-old Baloch man who—like many others in the region, was ID-less and stuck in poverty—was shot by snipers in Zahedan and denied medical care, thus sparking the outrage of Iranians across the country.¹⁵ The massacres of ethnic protestors even motivated high-ranking Sunni leaders, such as Maulavi Abudlhamid, to publicly speak out against Khamenei at Friday prayers.¹⁶ Moreover, long excluded from society and discriminated against as second-class citizens, members of the Baha’i faith and refugees from Afghanistan joined the protests, hoping to secure the right to exist and establish solidarity with other Iranians.¹⁷

Finally, Azizi discusses demands for environmental protections, freedom of intellectual and artistic expression, and geopolitical peace as part of the desire for a “normal life.” He details the stories of arrested environmental activists who sought to preserve wildlife, actresses convicted of violating censorship laws by showing their hair on Instagram, and the murders of authors and intellectuals following Khomeini’s declaration to “break the pens” of dissenters.¹⁸ These events made their way into the slogans chanted by 2022 protestors, who lamented the drying Zayandeh Rud river in Isfahan, the death of cheetah cub Pirouz, and demands for the release of prominent artists from Evin prison. Likewise, Azizi emphasizes the precarity of the Islamic Republic’s increasingly unpopular foreign policy by recounting the chants of pensioners to “leave Syria alone” or the push among academics to recognize the state of Israel and denounce Russia’s aggression in Ukraine.¹⁹

In the final chapter, Azizi concludes that “ideologues don’t make revolutions. Ordinary people do.”²⁰ Canvassing the range of slogans shouted by the 2022 protestors throughout the book, he paints a convincing picture of Iranians who simply want normalcy, i.e., freedom to exist as women and minorities, freedom to express and think, and freedom to live in a clean environment and a peaceful world. He draws on the online diary of 16-year-old Sarina Esmayilzadeh, who was killed while protesting in Karaj, to argue that the youth of the 2022 movement simply want to live hopeful and fun lives like “the teenagers living in New York or Los Angeles.”²¹ This claim is corroborated by many other analysts of the movement, including Sadeghi-Boroujerdi, Bayat, and Dabiri.²² As such, Azizi likens the 2022 uprisings to the 1906 Constitutional Revolution rather than the ideologically driven (i.e., Islamist, Marxist, and anti-monarchist) 1979 Revolution.²³ Specifically, dissatisfaction with arbitrary despotic

¹⁵ Azizi, 137.

¹⁶ Azizi, 140.

¹⁷ Azizi, 148, 167.

¹⁸ Azizi, 99, 106, 123.

¹⁹ Azizi, 173, 185, 188.

²⁰ Azizi, 195.

²¹ Azizi, 203.

²² Sadeghi-Boroujerdi, “Iran’s Uprisings for ‘Women, Life, Freedom’”; Asef Bayat, “A New Iran Has Been Born — A Global Iran,” *New Lines Magazine* (blog), October 26, 2022, <https://newlinesmag.com/argument/a-new-iran-has-been-born-a-global-iran/>; Arastoo Dabiri, “‘Woman, Life, Freedom’: A Movement in Progress in Iran,” *Dignity: A Journal of Analysis of Exploitation and Violence* 8, no. 1 (March 2023), <https://doi.org/10.23860/dignity.2023.08.01.05>

²³ Azizi, *What Iranians Want*, 207.

rule, foreign interference, and economic exploitation prompted the coalescing of various groups in 1906, including “wealthy merchants and street peddlers, [...] Persians and non-Persians, [...] Sunnis and Shi’is, [and] bazaaris in the capital and bazaaris in the provinces,” who successfully pressured the Qajar government to ratify the constitution.²⁴ Insofar as both movements joined disparate parts of society to demand a range of political freedoms, Azizi draws a plausible parallel between the 2022 uprisings and the 1906 Constitutional Revolution.

Although his final chapter effectively encompasses the various themes discussed, the book would further benefit from a guiding theme to create continuity between chapters. To a large extent, the lack of an explicit analytical lens causes the book to read like a series of disjointed facts, figures, and stories that—while interesting and insightful in their own right—can lose sight of the socially *interconnected* nature of the 2022 uprisings that set them apart from prior movements. Azizi briefly mentions Asfēf Bayāt’s *Life as Politics* in the preface of his book, but never explicitly adopts Bayāt’s conceptual framework in the subsequent chapters. Azizi’s nod to Bayāt is appropriate, given the relevance of *Life as Politics*’ “social nonmovements,” defined as the “collective action of non-collective actors,” in understanding how individual moments of resistance (such as ‘bad hijab’) can grow into a mass movement.²⁵ Azizi’s analysis would be strengthened by direct use of Bayāt’s concepts like the “*multitude*,” a term that views shared identity as deriving from tacit recognition of a shared struggle, as opposed to a totalizing unified “class” or “masses.”²⁶ Accordingly, the 2022 uprisings can be classified as the eruption of “collective politics” into sustained activism that targeted a weakened government, supporting Azizi’s argument that the uprisings were synergistic and non-ideological.²⁷ Despite allusions to the shared characteristics of various protesting groups, such as their marginalized positions, shared experiences in prison, or dissatisfaction with socioeconomic conditions, Azizi does not tie these loose threads, thus relying too heavily on the reader to make the connections.

Moreover, while he explicitly presents the uprisings as a “woman’s revolution,” Azizi fails to substantively discuss the role of women throughout the third, fourth, and sixth chapters. It is important not to lose sight of this, as it is precisely the “women’s issue” that set the 2022 uprisings apart from other political movements across the Middle East—and it is from this issue that the movement derived its strength.²⁸ Indeed, as Azizi acknowledges, the power of this movement stemmed from the shared experience of womanhood in Iran, which transcends political, religious, and socioeconomic boundaries.²⁹ Expanding beyond Azizi’s analysis, the significance of this

²⁴ Ervand Abrahamian, *Iran between Two Revolutions* (Princeton University Press, c1982), 92, <https://hdl.handle.net/2027/heb00853.0001.001>

²⁵ Asfēf Bayāt, *Life as Politics: How Ordinary People Change the Middle East, Second Edition* (Stanford University Press, 2013), 2, <https://doi.org/10.1515/9780804786331>

²⁶ Bayāt, 30.

²⁷ *Ibid.*

²⁸ Robin Wright, “Iran’s Protests Are the First Counter-Revolution Led by Women,” *The New Yorker*, October 9, 2022, <https://www.newyorker.com/news/daily-comment/irans-protests-are-the-first-counterrevolution-led-by-women>

²⁹ Azizi, *What Iranians Want*, 57.

being a woman's revolution and the ubiquity of the slogan "Zan, Zendegi, Azadi" throughout the protests is twofold: first, it places women's rights at the forefront of the revolution; and second, its breadth and ambiguity enable it to act as a unifying rallying call for a variety of oppressed or dissatisfied groups who can empathize with women's desires to live unrestricted and joyful lives.³⁰

Esfandar Sadeghi-Boroujerdi also proposes a theoretical framework that could be simplified into a guiding idea to fit Azizi's chosen themes and examples. Echoing Bayat, Sadeghi-Boroujerdi takes the uprisings to be a series of "social non-movements" that have been joined by more established ideological and political movements.³¹ Building on the theories of Louis Althusser and Stuart Hall, he argues that this "revolutionary rupture" derives from structural causes rather than sequential ones and so must be "understood as over-determined and the coming together of multiple contradictions."³² Sadeghi-Boroujerdi consequently outlines four primary contradictions that align with Azizi's chapters: 1. the crisis of gendered social control and reproduction; 2. the crisis of the nation-state (i.e. ethnic discrimination); 3. the crisis of "religious democracy" and the defeat of Reformist political faction; and 4. the crisis of authoritarian neoliberalism (i.e. economic corruption).³³ Azizi's book helpfully expands on the geopolitical and environmental crises, which Sadeghi-Boroujerdi briefly acknowledges. Sadeghi-Boroujerdi also provides key context for Azizi's discussion of weakening labour power and Reformism by explaining the militarization of provinces and "Islamic Keynesianism" that followed the Iran-Iraq War,³⁴ as well as the increasing role of parastatal organizations that derive power from non-elected political actors (such as the Guardian Council).³⁵ Providing a common thread inspired by this framework—centring both the Islamic Revolution and the contradictory state structures it produced—would strengthen the book by explicitly contextualizing the significance of each set of demands that constitute the call for "a normal life". This would aid the reader in connecting the pieces of the Iranian puzzle, from the 1906 and 1979 Revolutions to the 2022 uprisings, while avoiding the trap of totalizing claims about the universal desires of "all" Iranians that Azizi is (rightfully) wary of.

To conclude, *What the Iranians Want* is a largely successful attempt at contextualizing the 2022 uprisings for a general foreign audience. Its primary strengths lie in the organization and canvassing of a range of themes—including hijab compulsion, women's rights, labour unions, the environment, freedom of expression, freedom of religion, refugee rights, and peace—that rang through the slogans chanted by hundreds of thousands of protesters across Iran and its diaspora. Azizi's method of presenting specific slogans, activists, movements, and stories captivates the reader and conveys the deeply emotional impact of this fight for freedom. To create greater

³⁰ Bayat, "A New Iran Has Been Born — A Global Iran."

³¹ Sadeghi-Boroujerdi, "Iran's Uprisings for 'Women, Life, Freedom,'" 405.

³² Sadeghi-Boroujerdi, 408.

³³ Sadeghi-Boroujerdi, 406.

³⁴ Sadeghi-Boroujerdi, 426.

³⁵ Sadeghi-Boroujerdi, 422.

continuity between chapters and prevent the readers from becoming distracted by various stories, Azizi could expand the introduction of the book to include a guiding theme, or at the very least, lead with the idea of “a normal life” as the driving impetus for the uprisings. Such a framework would underscore and contextualize the revolutionary significance of Azizi’s various stories while consolidating the paradoxes inherent to the Iranian state that have prompted widespread protests. Overall, *What the Iranians Want* is a constructive and concise book for those looking to better understand the momentous “Women, Life, Freedom” uprisings.

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